

THE EFFECTS OF MICROTEACHING PRACTICES ON PRE-SERVICE PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION

Uğur Abakay¹ⁱ, Fikret Alincak¹, Hayri Demir²

¹Gaziantep University, Physical Education and Sport Department, Gaziantep, Turkey

²Selçuk University, Faculty of Sport Sciences, Konya, Turkey

Abstract:

The present research is a descriptive study, conducted in order to define the effects of microteaching practices on pre-service physical education and sports teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession. The research was conducted on 60 individuals, who studied at Gaziantep University, Department of Physical Education and Sports Teaching and took Special Teaching Methods II course in 2015-2016 academic year. In order to collect data for the present research, "Attitude Scale towards the Profession of Teaching" developed by Üstüner (2006) was employed. For data collection, a 13-week microteaching practice was implemented on pre-service physical education and sports teachers. Data collection tool was implemented on the work group twice, before and after the implementation. Collected data were analysed on SPSS 22.0 program. Paired-Samples t test was utilized as the statistical method. According to the obtained findings, pre-service teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession are high (positive), and microteaching practice affected pre-service physical education and sports teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession positively.

Keywords: microteaching, physical education, sports, pre-service teacher

Introduction

Education is the oldest concept in the history, which dates back to the ancient times and reaches today. Societies that existed since the creation of the world until today

¹ Correspondence: email uabakay@gmail.com

maintained their existence by transferring the values they created to new generations (Karaman, 2014; Abakay, 2013).

Education is defined as the studies conducted to develop the mind and body, emotional and social skills and behaviours in the most appropriate or desired direction, while teaching is defined as transferring of knowledge by teachers to students using educational tools in an organized and regular manner, generally at a teaching institution (Akyüz, 2013).

The purpose of education is developing the knowledge and skills of individuals for their adaptation to the society they are in and the outer world. Individuals need to be educated in a way that they can affect the contemporary developments. This is only possible with a good educational system and a qualified teaching staff. Teachers' being skills is important yet not enough (Dilaver, 1996). Balanced, effective and efficient employment of teachers, and enhancing their working and living conditions are as important (Çelikten, 2005). Pre-service teachers experience anxiety during teaching practices. From this perspective, microteaching practices are effective in preparing teachers for classroom experiences and reducing the anxiety they experience at the beginning of their professional life (Külahçı, 1994; Kuran, 2009; Uzunboylu and Hürsen 2011).

Method variety is a universal rule for effective teaching. There are no limits for the number of methods to be used in effective teaching. Teachers can develop new methods using their skills (Küçükahmet, 2004). For this reason, teachers should be able to make use of active student based methods, such as cooperative teaching, brainstorming, discussion, creating conceptual maps, creative drama, programmed teaching, computer assisted teaching and micro-teaching. Microteaching combines theoretical studies with practical studies in teacher education and aims at effective activities. Pre-service teachers are both teachers and students in this method. There is the cycle of teach-reteach. Pre-service teachers plan and teach the subject they choose. In accordance with the critics and evaluations provided for their teaching, they re-plan and reteach their lesson (Koçak et al., 2005).

Considering the positive reflections of the qualified teachers on student achievement in qualified education, many reforming movements intended for both teacher training system and teaching processes have been developed periodically in the last century (Lukin et al., 2004). For a successful teacher-training program, providing pre-service teachers with effective learning and teaching tactics and experiences should be the objective (İsmail, 2011). In terms of this objective, the purpose of microteaching practices can be defined as encouraging prospective teachers in the classroom about their attitudes and skills (Şen, 2010). The main objective of microteaching practices used

in the classroom is providing pre-service teachers with the important knowledge, skills and behaviours before they start their service (Demirel, 2009). The purpose of microteaching is making pre-service teachers bring their knowledge and skills to bear, have experience, develop their research skills, increase their self-confidence, decrease their anxiety, and make self-assessment (Galanouli et al., 2004; Güven, 2011).

Success motivation is important in individual or work life (Abakay, 2010; Abakay and Kuru, 2010; Abakay and Kuru, 2013). Microteaching aims at making pre-service teachers adopt and acquire the roles and behaviours they will have in the classroom with success motivation. One of the most important elements of microteaching is assessment through video recordings. Video is a tool used during microteaching practices for performance enhancement. During the assessment, the mistakes and lacking points are emphasized (Kpanja, 2001).

Many researchers defined microteaching in different ways. Enver (1990) defined it as a recorded practice system that emphasizes certain teaching skills and practices teaching process in limited conditions, and Allen (1980) defined microteaching as *“a recorded practical implementation system that emphasizes certain teaching skills and implements teaching process in limited conditions”*. According to Deniz (1993), microteaching is a laboratory method used to simplify the complexity of normal teaching-learning processes. Jerich (1989) defined microteaching as *“a teaching method, which supports pre-service teachers with strong feedbacks about their teaching in an environment where complex teaching environment is simplified”*. Rıza (1990) defined microteaching a recorded implementation system based on implementing certain teaching skills in limited conditions. *“Microteaching helps pre-service teachers develop their professional skills before they starts service”* (Tok, 2007). According to Küçükahmet (2004) microteaching is method that aims at helping pre-service teachers develop teacher identities and research skills.

Microteaching practices are not only used in teacher training but also many other fields, especially in medicine education. In his research, Deniz (1995) studied the use of microteaching practices in practising physician training, and found that limited teaching skills used in microteaching course were used more accurately and effectively after implementations. He also found that besides teaching skills, behaviours related to criticizing and being criticized also developed with microteaching course.

The common point of all definitions provided above is that microteaching is a method that provides teaching experiences in a safe, controlled and limited environment. In broader terms, microteaching enables presenting something and analysing the results of these presentations (Kazu 1996).

However, there are some studies for physical education and sport teacher candidates in educational field (Cinpolat et al., 2016; Alıncak, 2016a; Zengin et al., 2016), the studies on pre-service teachers are insufficient. Since microteaching practices are used to put theoretical knowledge into practice, they have an important place in both preparation to teaching profession and in other fields. Considering the importance of microteaching practices, the purpose of the present research is defining pre-service physical education and sport teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession before and after microteaching practices.

Method

The present research is a descriptive study that has been used in literature (Alıncak, 2016b) conducted in order to define the effects of microteaching practices on pre-service physical education and sport teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession. The research was conducted on 60 pre-service teachers, who studied at Gaziantep University, Department of Physical Education and Sports Teaching and took Special Teaching Methods II course in 2015/2016 academic year. In order to collect data for the present research, "*Attitude Scale towards the Profession of Teaching*" developed by Üstüner (2006) was employed. The scale consists of 34 items that reflect attitudes towards teaching profession. The scale is single dimensional and the highest score from the scale is 170 while the lowest is 34. Higher scores on the scale indicate more positive and lower scores indicate more negative attitudes towards teaching profession. Criterion validity of the scale was reported as ".89", score consistency coefficient as ".72", and internal consistency coefficient was reported as ".93" (Üstüner, 2006). Within the scope of the present research, reliability coefficient of the scale was calculated as .96. For data collection, a 13-week microteaching practice was implemented with pre-service physical education and sport teachers. The scale was conducted twice before and after the implementation on the work group as pre-test and post-test. Obtained data were analysed on SPSS 22.0 program. Statistical method used for data analysis was Paired-Samples t test.

Findings

Table 1: Comparison of pre-test and post-test scores of work group

	N	Average	sd	t	df	p
Pre-test	60	4.02	.48	-6.168	59	.000
Post-test	60	4.48	.52			

Table 1 presents the comparison of the pre-test and post-test scale scores of the work group. Accordingly, pre-service physical education and sport teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession varied at a significant level after the microteaching practices ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, according to the average scores presented in Table 1, pre-service physical education and sport teachers' scores for attitudes towards teaching profession ($X_{\text{pretest}} = 4.02 \pm .48$, $X_{\text{posttest}} = 4.48 \pm .52$) are high, which indicate more positive attitudes.

Discussion and Conclusion

According to the findings obtained in the present research, conducted in order to define the effects of microteaching practices on pre-service physical education and sport teachers' attitudes towards teaching profession, pre-service physical education and sport teachers' attitudes towards teaching education were high (positive) before and after microteaching practices. Moreover, there has been a significant increase in scores of attitudes towards teaching profession after microteaching practices.

Kuran (2009) reported in her study titled "*The Effect of Microteaching on Teachers' Gaining of Knowledge and Skills*", conducted to study the effects of microteaching on pre-service teachers' acquiring teaching knowledge and skills on 136 university sophomore students, that pre-service teachers were more successful in putting the acquired knowledge and skills related to teaching profession into practice. She also observed that microteaching contributed a lot to pre-service teachers' love for teaching profession.

According to the findings of the study titled "*The Teacher Candidates' Opinions Regarding the Effect of Microteaching Implementation on Teaching Skills*" conducted on 40 pre-service teachers by Küçüköğlü, Köse, Taşgın, Yılmaz and Karademir (2012), pre-service teachers, who had microteaching experiences, had less difficulty in performing teaching skills than pre-service teachers, who didn't have microteaching experiences. According to their finding, microteaching practices have positive effects on pre-service teachers' teaching skills.

Gürbüzöğlü, Yalınacı and Aydın (2014) studied with 16 pre-service teachers in their study titled "*The Views of Turkish Pre-service Science Teachers Concerning Microteaching Practices*" and took pre-service science teachers' ideas about microteaching practices in order to find out what microteaching practices provided pre-service teachers with, and which aspects of these practices they liked most and least. According to their findings, pre-service teachers stated that microteaching was effective in performing various teaching activities, practicing classroom management and acquiring various personal development skills.

Sevim (2013) conducted a case study on 28 university students in his study titled “*Evaluation of Microteaching Applications through Student Teachers’ Views*” in order to define the advantages and disadvantages of microteaching practices used in teacher training from pre-service teachers’ perspectives, and found that pre-service teachers developed positive attitudes towards microteaching practices. Additionally, it was reported that microteaching was beneficial for pre-service teachers in solving the problems encountered while preparing for the lesson, presenting and teaching the lesson.

Consequently, the present research revealed that pre-service physical education and sport teachers have positive attitudes towards teaching profession and microteaching practices affect pre-service physical education and sport teachers’ attitudes towards teaching profession positively.

In accordance with these findings, we can claim that more microteaching-based practices should be included in teacher training programs and practical courses, and organizing educational environments where effective microteaching activities can be conducted can contribute to pre-service teachers’ attitudes towards profession.

References

1. Abakay, U. (2010). Futbolcu-Antrenör İletişiminin Farklı Statülerdeki Futbolcuların Başarı Motivasyonu İlişkisi. Gazi University, Doctoral Thesis, Health Sciences Institution.
2. Abakay, U. (2013). Investigating Physical Education Teacher Candidates' Epistemological Beliefs. *Life Science Journal*, 10(3), 2658-64.
3. Abakay, U., Kuru, E. (2010). Profesyonel ve amatör futbolcuların statü değişkeni açısından başarı motivasyonu farklılıkları. *Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 4(3), 186-191.
4. Abakay, U., Kuru, E. (2013). Kadın Futbolcularda Antrenörle İletişim Düzeyi Ve Başarı Motivasyonu İlişkisi. *University of Gaziantep Journal of Social Sciences*, 12(1), 20-33.
5. Akyüz, Y. (2013). Türk eğitim tarihi (M.Ö.1000-M.S.2013). 25.baskı, Pegem Akademi. Ankara.
6. Alıncak, F. (2016a). Evaluation of opinions of primary school teachers on the method of education with game. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(3), 81-96.

7. Alıncak, F. (2016b). Attitudes of secondary school students including physical activity involving playing games. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(3), 1-14.
8. Alıncak, F., Uğurlu, F.M., Abakay, U., Ayan, S. (2016). Remarks of class teachers on game and physical activities lesson in terms of disabled students. *International Journal of Sport Studies*, 6(7), 460-467.
9. Allen, D.W. (1980). "Micro-teaching: Personal review". *British Journal of Teacher Education*, 6(2), 147- 151.
10. Çelikten, M. (2005). Öğretmenlik mesleği ve özellikleri. Pegem A Yay., Ankara.
11. Cinpolat, T., Alıncak, F., Abakay, U. (2016). Beden eğitimi ve spor yüksekokulu öğrencilerinin öğretmenlik mesleğine yönelik tutumlarının incelenmesi. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1(1), 38-47.
12. Demirel, Ö. (2009). Öğretme sanatı (14. Baskı). Ankara: PegemA Yayınları.
13. Deniz, L. (1993). Mikro öğretim. M.Ü. Atatürk Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi, 5,31-46.
14. Deniz, L. (1995). Bir mikroöğretim uygulaması ve değerlendirmesi "Hekim Eğiticilerin Eğitimi" hizmetiçi eğitim kursunda yapılan uygulama. M.Ü. Atatürk eğitim fakültesi eğitim bilimleri dergisi, 7, 61-66.
15. Dilaver, H. (1996). Türkiye'de öğretmen istihdamının dünü, bugünü ve yarını, Eğitimimize Bakışlar, İstanbul: Kültür Koleji Vakfı Yayınları 1, 119.
16. Enver, R. T. (1990). Eğitimde yöntemler teknolojisi. İzmir: Karınca Matbaası.
17. Galanouli, D., Murphy, C., Gardner, J. (2004). Teachers'perceptions of the effectiveness of ICT-competence training. *Computers & Education*, 42(1-2):63-79.
18. Gürbüzöğlü Yalınacı, S. ve Aydın, S. (2014) (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının mikro öğretim uygulamalarına yönelik görüşleri. *Turkish journal of education*, 3.
19. Güven, M. (2011). Öğrenme-öğretme süreci, öğretim ilke ve yöntemleri. (Edt: B. Duman) Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık. ss. 154-261.
20. İsmail, S.A.A. (2011). Student teachers' microteaching experiences in a pre-service English teacher education program. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 2(5), 1043-1051.
21. Jerich, K. (1989). Using a clinical supervision model for micro-teaching experiences. *Action in Teacher Education*, 11 (3), 24-31.
22. Karaman, P. (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının ölçme-değerlendirme okur-yazarlıklarının belirlenmesi ve mikro öğretim yoluyla geliştirilmesi. Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Doktora Tezi.

23. Kazu, H. (1996). Öğretmen yetiştirmede mikro öğretim yönteminin etkililiği(F.ü. teknik eğitim fakültesi örneği). Doktora tezi, Fırat üniversitesi sosyal bilimler enstitüsü, Elazığ, Türkiye.
24. Koçak, S.R., Eroğlu, Ö., Akyol, M., Anka, H. (2005). Öğretmen adayları için KPSS eğitim bilimleri, Asil Yayın Dağıtım Ltd. Şti., Ankara, Türkiye.
25. Kpanja, E. (2001). A study of the effects of video tape recording in microteaching training. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 32(4), 483-486.
26. Kuran, K. (2009). Mikro öğretimin öğretmenlik meslek bilgi ve becerilerinin kazanılmasına etkisi. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 6(11), 384-401.
27. Küçükahmet, L. (2004). Öğretimde planlama ve değerlendirme. İstanbul: Alkım yayınları.
28. Küçükkoğlu, A., Köse, E., Taşgın, A., Yılmaz, B. Y. ve Karademir, Ş. (2012). Mikro öğretim uygulamasının öğretim becerilerine etkisine ilişkin öğretmen adayı görüşleri. *Eğitim bilimleri araştırmaları dergisi*, 2(2).
29. Külahçı, S.G. (1994). Mikro öğretimde Fırat Üniversitesi Teknik Eğitim Fakültesi deneyimi II. değerlendirme. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 18 (92), 36-44.
30. Lukin, L.E., Bandalos, D.L., Eckhout, T.J. (2004). Facilitating the development of Assessment Literacy. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 23(2), 26-32.
31. Rıza, E. T. (1990). Eğitimde yöntemler teknolojisi. Karınca Matbaacılık. İzmir.
32. Sevim, S. (2013). Mikro öğretim uygulamasının öğretmen adayları gözüyle değerlendirilmesi, *Dicle üniversitesi Ziya Gökalp eğitim fakültesi dergisi*, 21(1).
33. Şen, A.İ (2010). Effect of peer teaching and microteaching on teaching skills of pre-service physics teachers. *Education and Science*, 35 (155), 78-88.
34. Tok N.T. (2007). Etkili öğretim için yöntem ve teknikler. A. Doğanay (Editör). Öğretim ilke ve yöntemleri. (2. Baskı). Ankara: Pegem Yayıncılık.
35. Uzunboylu, H., Hürsen, Ç. (2011). Öğretim ilke ve yöntemleri. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
36. Zengin, Ö., Demir, H., Alıncak, F., Abakay, U. (2016). The evaluation of high school 12th grade students' opinions about the effectiveness of physical education classes. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(4), 1-16.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).